

Munir's Convergent Model of Reality

We often deny reality because we value ignorance over wisdom, choosing to see and hear only what aligns with our desires and beliefs. We also tend to network with people in power who may offer us materialistic opportunities, perpetuating a cycle of slavery. We crawl in fright between the fears of actual realities and fabricated realities.

According to Munir's Convergent Model of Reality, embracing reality is a multifaceted process shaped by our socio-cultural context. Our tendency towards confirmation bias and labeling others as toxic when their beliefs don't align with ours can hinder our progress toward understanding reality. In actuality, each of us harbors varying degrees of toxicity that thrive on domination.

There are three phases to embracing reality: fabrication, permeation, and conscious reality.

In the fabrication phase, individuals seek validation and approval by creating an image that appeases others. They may choose unethical means to maintain it, becoming adept at fabricating realities while concealing their true selves. They remain appalling and insecure for a long time failing to identify the actual cause of distress, but the pleasure they receive through praise and honor gives them utmost satisfaction. Most people continue living this phase throughout their lives.

During the second stage, individuals encounter complex nano and micro realities from both familiar and unfamiliar sources. Through repeated exposure and complex experiences, they begin to assimilate elements of actual reality. Instead of relying on a single source, they seek confirmation through multiple sources. This stage can unveil harsh truths about oneself or others, potentially resulting in isolation, silence, or even violence. Only a few people successfully navigate this phase.

In the final stage, known as conscious reality, individuals embrace personal identity. They recognize their strengths and areas for growth and let go of grudges, fears, and insecurities. They navigate the world with conscious filtration, prioritizing genuine reality over fabrication. These individuals develop resilience and disregard societal judgments while being outspoken in expressing realities or prefer silence. Their motivations may not necessarily be driven by conventional notions of success. Many people fail to reach this stage because they find comfort in virtual realities and become self-obsessed. To reach this stage, one needs to think independently and free oneself from expectations and affiliations.

